

CHARACTERIZATION OF UNDAMAGED AND DAMAGED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES IN ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELDS FOR INDUCTIVE CHARGING OF ELECTRIC VEHICLES

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Inductive charging for electric vehicles

- Inductive charging for electric vehicles will require a copper coil, which is to be structurally integrated into the electric vehicle's underbody.
- The anisotropic electrical and mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) could allow the use in electromagnetic fields.
- If CFRPs is used as structural material, impact damage caused by stones is a concern.
- Damaged and undamaged CFRP plates were placed inside an electromagnetic field to measure the eddy current behavior/density and to analyze the influence of impact damages.

Damage characterization and current density

Since impact damages, like broken fibers and delaminations change the conductivity at the impact location, the current density distribution will change

Broken fibers in the 0°-ply of the 100 x 100 x 4.1 mm [(0/90)₃]_{sym} ex-PAN Probe after impacted with 26.4 J

Thermography image before and after impact damage

The thermography images correlate with the shielding rate. After the impact, the "cooler" rectangular shape in the center was more pronounced and extended outwards.

Probe: 100 x 100 x 4.1 mm [(0/90)₃]_{sym} ex-PAN Probe, impacted with 26.4 J

Electromagnetic characterization

The shielding rates increase significantly after impacts at the "corner" position while impacts in the center had no significant changes of the shielding rates

Conclusion

Parameters influencing the higher shielding and heating rates after impact:

- Zones of high current density are sensitive the impact damages (Impact position in the boundary zone show higher influence than impacts in the center position)
- Fiber angle and stacking sequence (Layers of different fiber orientation should be grouped together or insulated to minimize shielding effects)
- Higher specific conductivity of the fiber material results in higher shielding rates
- Impact energy level